

H-bonding interactions between simple DNA base cytosine and formamide molecules (model of protein unit) : A density functional theory study

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Abstract : The molecular geometry of complexes C-F_n (n = 2-7) of cytosine with formamide molecules was calculated within the density functional theory using the B3LYP function at 6-31G(d) basis set level. It was found that the interaction with formamide molecules forming a locked chain around cytosine results in significant changes in its intramolecular geometry. An obvious effect of hydrogen-bonding cooperativity can be seen during the complex process. The most interesting geometrical change of cytosine upon the complex is the shortening of bond C4-N7 resulting from the strengthening of the conjugation between the π system of the cytosine ring and the lone pair of the nitrogen atom. The significant elongation of C1-O8 bond and the presence of weak C-H...O hydrogen bonds are also revealed.

Keywords : DNA, H-bonding, formamide, cytosine, density functional theory.

Introduction

Hydrogen bonds (HBs) play an important role in DNA and RNA structures and functions. The double helix of DNA is built based on pairs of hydrogen bonded purines and pyrimidines as AT and GC base pairs stacked along the helix axis. The structure of DNA and molecular interactions maintaining the structure and stability of DNA are among the most important questions in chemistry since the structure was discovered by Watson and Crick. The reason is simple. DNA stores and transfers genetic information. Being a carrier of the genetic information, DNA occupies a central and critical role in the development and functioning of living organisms. However, it is notable that DNA should interact with proteins¹⁻⁴. In fact, the secondary structure of a protein is mostly determined by HBs between amide N-H groups of one residue and C=O groups of another⁵. Numerous efforts have been made in understanding the function of hydrogen bonds in protein-DNA interactions⁶⁻¹¹.

Proteins are polymers of amino acids which react with each other to form a peptide bond (symbolized as R-CONH-R'). As the amide peptide bond is demonstrated

Fig. 1. The simulative structure of proteins binding to the DNA.

to be the functional group in polypeptide chains and proteins, we can design a simple model of peptide for biological system investigations by substituting H atoms for R (R') groups and reserving the functional groups (-CONH-) synchronously¹². Formamide contains both carbonyl and amino groups, and despite its simplicity, it contains the essential features of the peptide bond, and it is often used as a model, especially in theoretical studies¹³⁻¹⁹. Many studies related to it have been carried out theoretically and experimentally such as formamide-water and formamide-methanol can be used as model systems of protein-water and protein-solvent interactions during the past few years²⁰⁻²³. So it is a valuable subject to investigate the interactions between DNA and proteins.

C-F2

C-F3

C-F4

Fig. 2

Fig. 2. The optimized structures of the complexes of cytosine with formamide molecules at B3LYP/6-31G(d) basis level.

Table 1. The hydrogen bond lengths (Å) involved in the complexes at B3LYP/6-31G(d) basis level

X-H...Y	C-F ₂	C-F ₃	C-F ₄	C-F ₅	C-F ₆	C-F ₇
N(F1)-H...O ₈	1.813	1.840	1.833	1.818	1.695	1.707
N ₆ -H...O(F1)	1.804	1.804	1.817	1.837	1.899	1.855
N(F2)-H...N ₅	1.934	1.998	1.978	1.929	1.855	1.870
N ₇ -H...O(F2)	1.852	1.798	1.865	1.981	1.927	1.896
N(F3)-H...O ₈		1.931	1.902	1.873	1.788	1.797
N(F2)-H...O(F3)		1.925	1.888	1.890	1.833	1.834
N(F4)-H...O(F2)			1.920	1.798	1.730	1.754
N ₇ -H...O(F4)			1.967			
N(F5)-H...O(F4)				1.833	1.764	1.824
N ₇ -H...O(F5)				2.004	1.919	1.930
C ₃ -H...O(F5)				2.328	2.331	2.129
N(F6)-H...O(F1)					1.857	1.870
C ₂ -H...O(F6)					2.079	2.157
C(F5)-H...O(F7)						2.310
N(F7)-H...O(F6)						1.947

For example, Fig. 1 is a simulative structure of proteins binding to the DNA. In addition, multiple H-bonding has been proposed to be the driving force in the molecular recognition process in protein-nucleic acid complexes²⁴⁻²⁸. For these reasons, in this article, we have made an investigation on the H-bonding interactions of cytosine-formamide complexes.

Cytosine is one of the most important organic molecules of life as it forms an integral part of DNA and RNA. In DNA complex, cytosine is paired with guanine via three hydrogen bonds and if cytosine was replaced by another type of base, it may lead to the introduction of a wrong genetic code. Because of the simple structure of cytosine and its importance in DNA complex, considerable amount of theoretical researches has been conducted concerning the H-bonding interactions of guanine-cytosine pair⁴ and cytosine with water²⁹. As mentioned above, formamide is usually chosen as the backbone of proteins to study the biological systems exhibiting the peptide type of bonding and hydrogen bond interactions. In this work, the H-bonding interactions between cytosine and formamides are well analyzed. A particular issue which we would like to reveal in this paper is how significant are the changes in the geometry and charge distribution of the cytosine when it is surrounded by formamide molecules forming a chain around it.

Computational methods :

A procedure for building a complex of cytosine with formamide molecules is as follows. The configuration of all possible CF₁ complexes has been fully optimized, in our previous work and the most stable complex is determined. Then, a second formamide is added, and the CF₂ complex having the lowest energy is found in the same way. The procedure is repeated until the formamide molecules around cytosine form a closed chain. All the configurations of the complexes have been fully optimized using density functional theory with the B3LYP method at 6-31G(d) basis set which is proved to be capable of providing reliable data concerning hydrogen-bonded systems involving the DNA bases. Frequency calculations have been well performed to ensure that the systems represent true minima on the potential energy surface since no imaginary frequencies have been found.

For further analysis of the characteristics of the hydrogen bonds, the intermolecular interaction energy (E_{int}) can be calculated by eq. (1),

$$E_{int} = E_{AB} - (E_A + E_B) \quad (1)$$

where E_{AB} is the energy of the supersystem AB, E_A and E_B are the energies of the noninteracting monomer A and B, respectively. Here, it refers to the bonding energy for the last formamide added to the complex and can be defined as follows :

Table 2. The selected geometric parameters, bonding energies^a of the complexes at B3LYP/6-31G(d) basis level

	Isolated	C-F ₂	C-F ₃	C-F ₄	C-F ₅	C-F ₆	C-F ₇
Bond lengths (Å)							
C4-N7	1.366	1.344	1.341	1.332	1.333	1.335	1.333
C4-N5	1.319	1.337	1.340	1.348	1.348	1.368	1.370
C1-O8	1.220	1.241	1.248	1.255	1.258	1.291	1.292
C1-N5	1.373	1.362	1.356	1.350	1.349	1.352	1.352
C1-N6	1.430	1.404	1.401	1.396	1.392	1.392	1.391
C2-N6	1.355	1.355	1.356	1.360	1.363	1.377	1.376
C2-C3	1.359	1.360	1.358	1.358	1.356	1.362	1.358
N7-H13	1.011	1.029	1.035	1.026	1.023	1.024	1.024
N7-H12	1.009	1.008	1.008	1.018	1.019	1.020	1.022
N6-H11	1.011	1.034	1.033	1.032	1.031	1.025	1.025
C2-H9	1.086	1.085	1.085	1.085	1.085	1.085	1.084
C3-H10	1.083	1.083	1.083	1.083	1.082	1.081	1.080
Bond angles (°)							
Σ(N(7)H ₂)	353.2	360.0	359.9	358.6	359.9	359.9	359.9
N6-C1-N5	116.0	117.8	118.3	118.7	118.9	119.2	119.3
C1-N5-C4	120.3	120.8	120.5	120.5	120.5	120.5	120.2
N5-C4-C3	124.2	122.0	121.9	121.6	121.5	120.6	120.7
C4-C3-C2	116.0	116.5	116.7	116.7	116.7	117.9	117.8
C3-C2-N6	119.9	120.7	120.7	120.8	120.9	120.0	120.1
C2-N6-C1	123.5	121.9	121.8	121.6	121.5	121.7	121.7
N6-C1-O8	118.2	119.7	118.7	118.4	118.3	118.4	117.9
N5-C4-N7	116.9	117.6	117.9	117.6	118.5	118.4	119.0
Dihedral angles (°)							
N5-C4-N7-H13	11.4	-0.1	-1.6	6.0	1.4	1.3	1.0
O8-C1-N6-H11	0.0	0.0	0.7	-0.5	-0.8	-0.7	-2.5
H11-N6-C2-H9	0.1	0.0	-0.7	0.9	0.9	0.8	1.5
C2-N6-C1-N5	-0.3	0.0	-0.3	0.6	0.1	-0.4	-0.8
Binding energies (kcal mol⁻¹)							
			-14.41	-14.67	-13.84	-12.25	-12.11
			(-12.49)	(-12.84)	(-13.93)	(-10.37)	(-10.34)

^aBSSE – corrected values in parentheses.

$$E_{B(C-F_n)} = E_{C-F_n} - (E_{C-F_{n-1}} + E_F) \quad (2)$$

where n = 3–7. In order to eliminate the basis set superposition errors (BSSE) produced in the calculations of interaction energy, the Boys-Bernardi Counterpoise (CP) technique was employed. The natural population atomic (NPA) charges have been determined at the same basis set level. All computations were performed using the Gaussian 98 program.

Results and discussion

The optimized configurations of the cytosine complexes

with formamide molecules are presented in Fig. 2. The corresponding geometric parameters of the complexes are given in Table 1. As can be seen from Fig. 2, all the formamide molecules may be divided into two groups. The first group includes those who can form hydrogen bonds with cytosine and the second group is the formamide molecules which acts as bridge between the formamide molecules hydrogen-bonded to cytosine. All of the formamide molecules are not only a proton-donor but also a proton receptor and prefer to be N–H proton donor rather than C–H proton donor. It is found that the

Table 3. The charge distributions on cytosine molecule at B3LYP/6-31G(d) basis level

Charge distribution (e)	Isolated	C-F ₂	C-F ₃	C-F ₄	C-F ₅	C-F ₆	C-F ₇
O8	-0.516	-0.575	-0.585	-0.608	-0.617	-0.614	-0.614
C1	0.692	0.734	0.734	0.744	0.747	0.661	0.662
N5	-0.558	-0.622	-0.607	-0.618	-0.622	-0.554	-0.540
C4	0.520	0.576	0.573	0.573	0.552	0.463	0.457
N7	-0.762	-0.811	-0.808	-0.839	-0.823	-0.789	-0.783
H13	0.350	0.407	0.411	0.390	0.393	0.378	0.377
H12	0.334	0.334	0.334	0.386	0.390	0.376	0.380
H10	0.138	0.139	0.142	0.157	0.189	0.195	0.214
C3	-0.223	-0.229	-0.226	-0.217	-0.226	-0.155	-0.160
C2	0.125	0.114	0.113	0.108	0.101	0.103	0.097
H9	0.170	0.178	0.179	0.179	0.174	0.247	0.221
N6	-0.614	-0.653	-0.651	-0.653	-0.653	-0.707	-0.709
H11	0.344	0.398	0.397	0.397	0.394	0.382	0.337
Total	0.0	-0.01	0.006	-0.001	-0.001	-0.004	-0.021

formamide molecules are preferentially bound to the CONH fragment of cytosine which makes it easier to donate or accept protons to form hydrogen bonds. From the Fig. 2, we can see that the CF₂ is a planar complex, but when more formamide molecules are added, the structure of the complexes changes significantly.

A H-bond is usually denoted as X-H...Y, where X and Y are the H-bond donor and H-bond acceptor, respectively. It is well known that the energy of the hydrogen bond depends on the Y...H bond length and the X-H...Y bond angle. When the length of the bond is longer than 1.6 Å, the strength of the bond depends less on the value of the X-H...Y angle. All the values listed in Table 1 are the distances of Y...H of hydrogen bond X-H...Y. According to the differences of the monomers participating in the formation of H bonds, we divide all the H bonds involved in the complexes into two groups. The H bonds formed between cytosine and formamide molecules (HB_{sCF}) and the among formamide molecules (HB_{sFF}). As can be seen from Table 1, an analysis of the geometrical characteristics of H-bonds allows us to conclude that, in general, the hydrogen bonds between the formamide molecules are stronger than the bonds between cytosine and formamide. But the former located around the hydrophobic region of

cytosine are weaker compared with other sites. For C-F7 complex, the bond lengths of N(F7)-H...O(F6) and C(F5)-H...O(F7) which located around the hydrophobic region of cytosine are 1.947 Å and 2.301 Å, but the bond lengths of N(F5)-H...O(F4), N(F4)-H...O(F2) and N(F2)-H...O(F3) which are located at the other sites of cytosine are 1.824 Å, 1.754 Å, 1.834 Å, respectively. So the strength of the H-bonds between formamide molecules also depends on the specific sites of the location of the formamide. An extensively investigated phenomenon called "cooperativity of H-bonds"³⁰⁻³³ has been hypothesized by a proximity effect, which is the entropy required to bond the neighboring groups has been decreased by the already accomplished bonds³³ and it is expected to be a key in the displacement of the formamide molecules to one side of cytosine mean plane. The strongest H-bonds are formed by CONH fragment of cytosine. The amino group and the N(5) atom of the pyrimidine ring form a relatively weaker hydrogen bonds. An analysis of the structure of complex C-F7 reveals that the distances between the hydrogen atoms at the C₂-C₃ double bond of cytosine and F5, F6 molecules and their mutual orientation indicate the existence of weak C-H...O bonding. It is also found that all the H-bonds involving the participation of C-H bonds beyond 2.2 Å are less stable than other H-bonds

generally within 2.1 Å. Such interactions provide additional contribution to the total binding energy.

Table 2 demonstrates the geometrical changes of cytosine during the complex process as well as the hydrogen bonding energies. The NPA charge distributions on cytosine are calculated for its relationship with the recognition between bases and proteins³⁴, and are listed in Table 3.

As can be seen from Table 2, the increasing formamide molecules have little effect on the geometry of cytosine. For most of the complexes changes in bond lengths and bond angles are less than 0.01 Å and 1°, respectively, but a comparison of isolated molecule and complexes demonstrates that the interaction with formamide molecules significantly influence its molecular structure. The deformation of the bonds mainly occurs in the regions of strong hydrogen bonds with some elongations of the C4–N5 (0.018–0.051 Å) and C1–O8 (0.021–0.072 Å) bonds. The significant elongation of C1–O8 bond is up to 1.292 Å. This value is typical for a single C–O⁻ bond (carboxyl anion of general value is 1.255 Å). Therefore, this bond may be considered as a single C–O⁻ bond rather than a double bond. The C1–N6 and C4–N5 bonds are essentially shorter and in the regions of 0.026–0.049 Å, 0.011–0.023 Å, respectively. The C4–N7 bond in the complex molecule is shorter compared with isolated cytosine and its length is closer to the mean value of C=N double bond (1.281 Å) than to the C–N single bond (1.416 Å). The shortening of C4–N7 bond is interesting for an increase in the degree of pyramidalicity of the amino group showed by the changes of the bond angles ΣNH_2 (at the N7) and dihedral angles involving the amino group is related to a change of the nitrogen atom hybridization from sp^2 to sp^3 and an elongation of C4–N7 bond. This is supposed to result from the strengthening of the conjugation between the π system of the cytosine ring and the lone pair of the nitrogen atom. In isolated cytosine, the double N5–C4 bond is essentially shorter than the single C1–N5 bond, while in C–F6, C–F7 complexes, the C1–N5 bond is shorter than N5–C4 bond and the N5–C4 bond length (1.368, 1.370 Å) is closer to the average value for the single C–N bond (1.376 Å). There is hardly any influence found on bonds C3–H10 and C2–H9.

For the formamide molecules, we divide all the H-bonds involved in the complexes into two groups – the H-bonds formed between cytosine and formamide molecules (HBs_{CF}) and those among formamide molecules (HBs_{FF}). The H-bonds are O in the C=O for the acceptor and H in the NH_2 for the donor. The deformation of the bonds mainly occurs in the regions of strong hydrogen bonds with some elongations of the C–N (0.018–0.0351 Å) and C–O (0.025–0.052 Å) bonds.

The binding energies of the complexes are also showed in Table 2. The bonding energy of C–F2 has not been calculated for the initial optimized structure and is obtained at a different basis set 6-311++G(d,p). From Table 2, we can see that the binding energies of the complexes are in order of C–F₄ (–14.67 kcal mol⁻¹) < C–F₃ (–14.41 kcal mol⁻¹) < C–F₅ (–13.84 kcal mol⁻¹) < C–F₆ (–12.25 kcal mol⁻¹) < C–F₇ (–12.11 kcal mol⁻¹), and the stability order of the complexes based on binding energy is C–F₄ > C–F₃ > C–F₅ > C–F₆ > C–F₇. In the C–F6 and the C–F7 complexes, there are weak C–H...O bonds. These bonds are characterized by longer O...H distances as compared with the conventional hydrogen bonds. As mentioned above, such interactions provide additional contribution to the total binding energy. Therefore the binding energies of the C–F6 and the C–F7 are more than the others. The stronger H bonding cooperativity is supposed to account for the specialities of C–F6 and C–F7, which needs further effort in our future work. Taking BSSE corrections into account, all the values have decreased showing a general importance of BSSE corrections in the calculation of bonding energy.

The values of total NPA charge distributions on cytosine of the complexes are displayed in Table 3. As can be seen from Table 3, the results of the calculation reveal that the changes in the atomic charges are rather small except for the oxygen atom. As mentioned above, the C1–O8 may be considered as a single C–O⁻ bond rather than a double bond. So the existence of the carbonyl group in the enolic form causes a considerable increase in negative charge on this atom. The total NPA charge distributions on cytosine of the complexes show that an electron charge transfer is from surrounding formamide molecules to

cytosine in complexes C-F₂, C-F₄, C-F₅, C-F₆ and C-F₇, whereas in C-F₃ complex, the electron charge transfer is from cytosine to the surrounding formamide molecules.

Conclusions :

The structures of hydrogen-bonded complexes C-F_n (n = 2-7) of cytosine with formamide molecules have been fully optimized at B3LYP/6-31G(d) basis set level. Our study reveals that the interaction of cytosine with formamide molecules results in significant changes in its intramolecular geometry. The most interesting geometrical change of cytosine upon the complex is the shortening of bond C4-N7 resulting from the strengthening of the conjugation between the π electron system of the cytosine ring and the lone pair of the nitrogen atom. The significant elongation of C1-O8 bond is up to 1292 Å. This value is typical for a single C-O bond (mean value for carboxylate anions is 1.255 Å). Therefore, this bond may be considered as a single C-O bond rather than a double bond. The binding energies of the complexes are in order of C-F₄ < C-F₃ < C-F₅ < C-F₆ < C-F₇. The existence of the weak C-H...O bonds and the stronger H-bonding cooperativity are supposed to account for the higher bonding energies of C-F₆ and C-F₇. The charge distributions on cytosine reveal that the changes in the atomic charges are rather small except for the oxygen atom. The existence of the carbonyl group in the enolic form causes a considerable increase in negative charge on this atom.

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